

Azərbaycan respublikasının qərb regionunda meyvəçiliyin müasir vəziyyəti və yüksəklik qurşaqları üzrə ərazi təşkili

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Xülasə: Məqalədə Azərbaycan Respublikasının qərb bölgəsində meyvəçiliyin müasir vəziyyəti və hündürlük qurşaqları üzrə ərazi təşkilindən bəhs olunur. Bu bölgə əlverişli təbii şəraitə malik olmaqla, meyvəçiliyin inkişaf etdiyi əsas regionlardan biri olmuşdur. Hazırda bəzi meyvə əkinlərinə və istehsalına görə (ərik, armud, xurma, gavalı, şaftalı, zoğal) qərb regionunda yerləşən Gəncə-Daşkəsən və Qazax-Tovuz iqtisadi rayonları ölkədə fərqlənilir.

Həmçinin məqalədə meyvəçiliyin son illərdəki əkin sahələrinin və istehsalının dinamikası verilmişdir. Müəyyən olunmuşdur ki, son on ildə meyvəçilikdə yüksək inkişaf getmiş, əkinlər genişlənməmiş, istehsal və məhsuldarlıq artmışdır. Hazırda ölkədə istehsal edilən meyvənin təxminən 1/5 hissəsi regionun payına düşür.

Bununla yanaşı regionda meyvəçiliyin hündürlük qurşaqları üzrə təhlili verilmiş və müəyyən olunmuşdur ki, 201-500 metr mütləq yüksəkliklərdə meyvəçilik daha yaxşı inkişaf etmişdir. Belə ki, meyvə bağlarının 57,3%-i, istehsalının isə 66,7%-i məhz bu hündürlük areallarında yerləşmişdir.

Hazırda iki iqtisadi rayonun (Gəncə-Daşkəsən və Tovuz-Qazax iqtisadi rayonları) yerləşdiyi regionda meyvəçiliyin inkişafı üçün kifayət qədər təbii şərait mövcud olsa da, müəyyən qədər çətinliklər də mövcuddur.

Açar sözlər: *iqtisadi rayon, kənd təsərrüfatı, meyvəçilik, yüksəklik qurşaqları, istehsal, məhsuldarlıq*

Current state of fruit growing in the western region of the Republic of Azerbaijan and its territorial organization by altitudinal zones

Abstract: This article examines the current state of fruit growing in the western region of the Republic of Azerbaijan and its territorial distribution by altitudinal zones. This region, having favorable natural conditions, is one of the main areas for the development of fruit growing. At present, for some types of fruit crops (apricot, pear, persimmon, plum, peach, cornelian cherry), the western region, in particular the Ganja-Dashkasan and Gazakh-Tovuz economic districts, stands out at the national level.

The article also presents the dynamics of cultivated areas and fruit production over recent years. It has been established that over the past ten years, fruit growing has significantly developed, with an increase in orchard areas, production, and yield. Currently, about one-fifth of the total fruit produced in the country comes from this region.

In addition, an analysis of fruit growing by altitudinal zones was conducted, revealing that fruit cultivation develops best at absolute altitudes of 201–500 meters. Specifically, 57.3% of orchards and 66.7% of production are concentrated in these altitudinal zones.

Although the region, which includes two economic districts (Ganja-Dashkasan and Tovuz-Gazakh), has quite favorable natural conditions for fruit growing, certain challenges also exist.

Keywords: *economic district, agriculture, fruit growing, altitudinal zones, production, yield*

Introduction

Fruit growing is one of the oldest branches of agriculture. The region's relief, soil, and climatic conditions have created favorable opportunities for the development of fruit growing. The advancement of this sector not only ensures the production of essential food products but also contributes to the increase of the population's income through the products obtained from its production. The development of fruit growing is highly significant for enhancing export potential within the country's agrarian sector.

As of the beginning of 2024, the stock balance of fruits and berries in Azerbaijan amounted to 25.2 thousand tons. A total of 1,317.9 thousand tons of fruits and berries were produced, while 202.4 thousand tons were imported. The country exported 444.6 thousand tons of fresh fruits and imported 155.7 thousand tons. Although revenues from the export of fresh fruits reached 484.8 million USD, the import expenditures amounted to 171.6 million USD. Currently, the self-sufficiency level in fruits and berries is 128.5% [2, p.33, 75; 4, p.182.]. The sustainable development of the fruit production cycle is considered one of the most profitable areas of agriculture. This sector plays an essential role in the development of the canning and confectionery industries, while also serving as an important source of fresh and processed food products. According to physiological consumption norms, each person should consume 120–125 kg of fruits and berries annually [Gurbanzadeh,2011: p.224].

Analysis and Discussion

In the Ganja–Dashkasan and Gazakh–Tovuz economic regions, fruit growing, as in other parts of the country, has developed considerably. Being a type of perennial cultivation, horticulture provides broad opportunities for the abundance of fruits and fruit-based products [Pashayev, 2010: p.303].

These regions account for 8.8% of the total fruit and berry cultivation area and 18.7% of their total production in the republic. Out of these plantations, 19.5 thousand hectares are occupied by fruit orchards and 0.7 thousand hectares by berry crops, while the total production reached 242.5 thousand tons of fruits and 4.5 thousand tons of berries.

Over the past decade, the area under fruit and berry plantations in these regions has steadily increased. Thus, the total area of fruit and berry cultivation in the economic regions has grown by 36.8%, expanding from 14.9 thousand hectares to 20.4 thousand hectares (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of fruit and berry cultivation in the western region of Azerbaijan (2014–2024)

The expansion of cultivated areas and the increase in productivity have led to a significant rise in overall production. Compared to 2014, production has increased by 84.2%, rising from 134.1 thousand tons to 247.0 thousand tons (Table) [6].

Table 1. Dynamics of fruit production and productivity in the western regions of Azerbaijan (2014-2024)

Districts	Production, ton			Productivity, cent/ha		
	2014	2024	Change, times	2014	2024	Change, times
Ganja city	550,7	813,9	1,5	57,0	28,2	-2,0
Gazakh	14185,5	16664,6	1,2	131,4	111,6	-1,1
Aghstafa	9667,1	15220,2	1,6	99,0	117,9	1,2
Tovuz	15224,0	23591,6	1,5	168,6	178,4	1,1
Shamkir	59994,8	106577,1	1,8	210,5	241,7	1,1
Gadabay	257,0	26628,8	103,6	0,9	83,0	92
Dashkasan	667,0	732,8	1,1	64,3	70,7	1,1
Samukh	13678,7	19653,9	1,4	131,5	112,4	-1,2
Goygol	1842,4	2891,4	1,6	30,9	39,8	1,3
Goranboy	17487,0	29597,0	1,7	64,9	85,2	1,3
Naftalan city	372,3	142,1	-2,6	148,9	12,2	-12,2
Total	134134,8	247029,0	1,8	100,4	126,5	1,3

Source: Agriculture of Azerbaijan, 2024 [1]

Fruits are cultivated across all altitudinal zones of the region, including farmlands and household plots. Currently, the districts of Samukh (2.4 thousand ha), Goranboy (3.4 thousand ha), Gadabay (3.7 thousand ha), and Shamkir (4.4 thousand ha) account for 71.3% of all orchards and 73.6% of fruit production in the western region, with the total orchard area exceeding 2 thousand hectares.

Over the past decade, fruit production in almost all administrative districts (excluding the city of Naftalan) has increased, with the most significant growth observed in Gadabay district. The substantial rise in productivity has directly contributed to the overall increase in production volume.

In 2024, the highest productivity was recorded in Shamkir district, reaching 241.7 centners per hectare (Table).

In the economic regions, the main fruits cultivated include apples, pears, quinces, apricots, cherries, sweet cherries, plums, cornelian cherries (dogwood), and figs. These regions stand out in Azerbaijan for the production of certain fruit types. For instance, the western regions account for 29.4% of apricot, 28.9% of pear, 38.0% of persimmon, 33.9% of plum, 34.8% of peach, and 69.6% of cornelian cherry production in the country.

Fruits produced in the economic regions are well recognized in foreign consumer markets. In particular, persimmons grown in the districts of Goranboy, Aghstafa, and other areas are successfully exported and sold abroad.

In the region, 9.2% of orchards and berry plantations and 7.1% of total production are located in the lowland areas at altitudes ranging from 0 to 200 meters above sea level. Among these, Samukh and Goranboy districts account for 29.2% and 34.9%, respectively, of the orchards and berry plantations in this zone.

The foothill plains, covering altitudes between 201- 500 meters, represent the main cultivation belt for many crops, including fruits and berries. This zone hosts 57.3% of orchards and berry plantations and 66.7% of the total production. In this belt are located all orchards within the cities of Naftalan and Ganja, as well as parts of those in Dashkasan (0.7%) and Goygol (12.5%) districts. The majority of orchards in Aghstafa (65.3%), Tovuz (71.4%), Samukh (68.4%), Gazakh (98.7%), Goranboy (66.7%), and Shamkir (91.4%) districts are also situated within this altitude range.

At medium mountain altitudes, 501–1000 meters, 8.5% of orchards and berry plantations and 7.4% of total production are located. Within this zone, orchards are distributed across Dashkasan (2.2% of the district's total planted area), Gazakh (1.3%), Shamkir (5.7%), Tovuz (14.3%), Goranboy (6.6%), Aghstafa (32.7%), and Goygol (64.5%) districts.

At absolute altitudes of 1001–1500 meters, 21.9% of the orchards and fruit plantations and 16.3% of the total production in the economic region are located. In this altitudinal belt, the majority of orchards and fruit plantations are concentrated in the Gadabay (89.2% of the district's total cultivated area) and Dashkasan (71.6%) districts. A smaller proportion of orchards in Tovuz (4.2%), Goygol, Shamkir, and Goranboy districts are also found within this elevation range.

At altitudes between 1501-2000 meters, 3.1% of orchards and fruit plantations are located, representing parts of those in Dashkasan (25.4%), Tovuz (6.7%), and Gadabay (11.4%) districts. Approximately 2.5% of total fruit production is obtained from this elevation zone (Figure 2).

Above 2000 meters above sea level, the heat resources gradually decrease, making it impossible to meet the thermal requirements of fruit trees. As a result, their vegetation process remains incomplete. These high-altitude areas are predominantly covered with grass vegetation and are mainly used as summer pastures.

Figure 2. Location of fruit growing by altitudinal zones in the Western regions of Azerbaijan

As is well known, in the mountainous areas there are wild fruit trees and berry shrubs growing naturally, which are also utilized by the local population. Nevertheless, in recent years, new orchards have been established in the economic regions, as envisaged in the state programs related to the development of the agrarian sector.

For these newly planted orchards, ensuring proper agro-technical maintenance and the application of innovative approaches is of great importance to promote their healthy development and achieve high productivity.

In this regard, the application of international experience to agriculture, particularly the use of artificial intelligence, can significantly contribute to productivity and sustainable development in the sector. AI-driven technologies enable farmers and entrepreneurs to monitor crop health, as well as weather and soil conditions, more effectively.

Such technologies help optimize water usage, fertilizer and pesticide application, minimize waste, and increase productivity. At the same time, AI-powered tools, drones, and robots equipped with image recognition technology can monitor plant conditions and detect crop diseases, nutrient deficiencies, and pests at early stages. This allows for timely intervention and prevents large-scale damage.

Moreover, robotic pesticide application systems target only affected areas, thereby optimizing the use of chemical substances. Also, by analyzing genetic data and environmental conditions, AI technologies assist in the cultivation of climate-resilient crop varieties, promoting adaptation to changing climatic factors.

In addition, automated soil analysis systems can assess nutrient levels, acidity, and other factors, allowing farmers to make more informed decisions about which crops to plant based on the analyzed data. Timely identification of these parameters enables agricultural producers to make data-driven decisions, reducing potential risks and uncertainties in farming practices. These systems also help prevent water waste, save energy, and increase productivity.

In the development of fruit growing, factors such as transportation, storage, processing, and marketing of products are also of great importance. In recent years, the establishment of agroparks and logistics centers in the region has played a major role in improving this field. However, despite the progress in fruit growing across administrative districts, certain challenges still persist. Once fruits are harvested, they must be processed using appropriate technologies or stored in refrigerated warehouses for a specific period to preserve their quality and profitability. Otherwise, products must be sold immediately after harvesting, which is often unprofitable for producers.

The absence of fruit processing enterprises in some districts, as well as the limited capacity of existing cold storage facilities to accommodate all produced fruits, creates serious constraints for the sustainable development of this sector.

Conclusion

A comparative analysis of the current state and spatial organization of fruit growing in the western regions of Azerbaijan has yielded the following conclusions:

The western regions of the country (Ganja–Dashkasan and Gazakh–Tovuz economic regions) stand out nationally in terms of the cultivation and production of certain fruits. Approximately 8.8% of the total fruit and berry cultivation area and 18.7% of total production in the country are located in these regions. Among the administrative districts, Samukh, Goranboy, Gadabay, and Shamkir have demonstrated the most advanced development in fruit growing.

In recent years, the total area of fruit and berry plantations in these economic regions has increased by 36.8%, while production has grown by 84.2%. The rise in production was influenced not only by the expansion of cultivated areas but also by the increase in productivity (26.0%).

The distribution of fruit growing by altitudinal zones has been investigated here for the first time. The results indicate that the zone covering altitudes of 201–500 meters represents the largest share in the spatial organization of fruit growing in these economic regions. More than half of the orchards (57.3%) and over one-third of production (66.7%) are located within this belt.

Overall, the western economic regions provide favorable conditions for the development of fruit growing across altitudinal zones. By effectively utilizing natural and economic factors, it is possible to overcome existing challenges and achieve further advancement in this sector.

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